

Unfolding Story of Teachers Towards Sleep Deprivation Related to Personality Development

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Abstract. Teachers' role in shaping society's future cannot be overstated. However, their well-being, particularly in terms of sleep deprivation, has received limited attention about its impact on their personality development, and the participants of the study are the 10 public elementary school teachers who would purposively be selected to serve as informants. The finding revealed that the teachers' lived experiences regarding sleep deprivation related to personality development have three major themes: impact on interpersonal skills, aspects of socially solid skills, and adverse effects on cognitive skills. While the teachers' coping mechanisms with the challenges they manage and the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation consider the two major themes of balancing workload and teachers' collaborative efforts at work. Educational management or insights are drawn from the study's findings, which have three major themes: Identify lifestyle habits, Support Colleagues at work, and Teacher Personality Development. Understanding the link between sleep deprivation and personality development underscores the need for a holistic approach to education. The research can guide the development of evidence-based interventions or programs to improve awareness among teachers towards sleep deprivation related to teacher personality development. Teachers may benefit from professional development and training on recognizing and addressing sleep-related issues. This can empower them with the knowledge and skills to support students in improving their sleep habits.

KEY WORDS

1. Unfolding story of teachers.
2. sleep deprivation
3. personality development

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1. Introduction

The unfolding story of teachers and sleep deprivation related to personality development is a compelling narrative that underscores the critical intersection of education and well-being in our society. Educators worldwide have grappled with an increasingly demanding profession marked by long hours, high-stakes expectations, and mounting responsibilities in recent years. This reality has given rise to a concerning trend of sleep deprivation among teachers. This phenomenon has far-reaching implications for both their personal lives and their ability to nurture the next generation's personality development. Teachers are entrusted with the profound responsibility of shaping young minds, imparting knowledge, and instilling values that help students grow into well-rounded individuals. However, the toll of sleep deprivation on

educators threatens their effectiveness in fulfilling this vital role. The lack of adequate sleep can adversely affect teachers' physical and mental health, diminishing their capacity to engage with students empathetically and constructively. The story also touches upon the broader societal implications of this issue. Sleep-deprived teachers not only face risks to their own well-being but may inadvertently contribute to the perpetuation of a culture that prioritizes academic achievement over holistic development. The very individuals responsible for nurturing young minds into well-rounded individuals may struggle to maintain their own well-roundedness due to sleep deprivation. In a global context, sleep deprivation is commonplace in modern society, but its far-reaching effects on cognitive performance are only beginning to be understood from a scientific perspective. While there is broad consensus that insufficient sleep leads to a general slowing of response speed and increased variability in performance, particularly for simple measures of alertness, attention and vigilance, there is much less agreement about the effects of sleep deprivation on many higher-level cognitive capacities, including perception, memory, and executive functions. Sleep deprivation often leads to irritability, reduced patience, and heightened stress levels. These adverse effects can spill over into the classroom, potentially hindering the nurturing of a positive and supportive learning environment. Moreover, teachers experiencing chronic sleep deprivation may find it challenging to maintain the creativity, resilience, and adaptability required to cater to diverse student needs and foster their holistic personality development. As we delve deeper into this story, we must explore the multifaceted factors contributing to teachers' sleep deprivation. The relentless demands of lesson planning, grading, meetings, and administrative tasks can lead to long workdays and nights, leaving little time for restorative sleep. Moreover, the emotional toll of dealing

with students' varied needs, societal pressures, and the ever-evolving landscape of education exacerbates the problem. In conclusion, the unfolding story of teachers and sleep deprivation related to personality development highlights the urgent need for a comprehensive dialogue and support system. Addressing the challenges educators face in maintaining a healthy work-life balance and ensuring adequate sleep is crucial for their well-being and fostering an environment where students can thrive emotionally, socially, and academically. As we unravel this narrative, it becomes clear that investing in the health and well-being of our educators is an essential step toward nurturing the holistic development of our future generations (Hinson JM., 2020). In the national context, central to this debate has been the question of whether sleep deprivation affects nearly all cognitive capacities in a rational manner through degraded alertness and attention or whether sleep loss specifically impairs some aspects of cognition more than others. Neuroimaging evidence has implicated the prefrontal cortex as a brain region that may be particularly susceptible to the effects of sleep loss. Still, perplexingly, executive function tasks that putatively measure prefrontal functioning have yielded inconsistent findings within the context of sleep deprivation (Gong et al., 2023). Supported by the idea of Shao (2020), whereas many convergent and rule-based reasoning, decision-making, and planning tasks are relatively unaffected by sleep loss, more creative, divergent, and innovative aspects of cognition do appear to be degraded by lack of sleep. Emerging evidence suggests that some aspects of higher-level cognitive capacities remain degraded by sleep deprivation despite restoration of alertness and vigilance with stimulant countermeasures, suggesting that sleep loss may affect specific cognitive systems above and beyond the effects. In the local context, studies report an alarming rate of insufficient sleep among college students. A survey

at a Philippine university in Manila and Colleagues (Lund et Al.,2019) found that up to 70% In Davao City, sleep deprivation has become a chronic problem in all Davao cities, especially for all students; since students have many things to do, such as papers, assignments, and projects that need effort and much time, students prefer to sacrifice their sleep in order to pass all the requirements on time, a study from Davao City National High School (2021). Thus, the extent to which sleep deprivation affects a particular cognitive process may depend on several factors, including the magnitude of the global decline in general alertness and attention and the degree to which the specific cognitive function depends on emotion-processing networks. In the article by Cureus (Publishing et al. 2019), they proposed that sleep deprivation causes depression, agitation, apathy, and poor academic performance in students. Reduced total sleeping hours have been associated with declining academic performance. Finally, the role of emotion as a critical facet of cognition has received increasing attention in recent years and mounting evidence suggests that sleep deprivation may particularly affect cognitive systems that rely on emotional data (Physical, 2023). Sleep deprivation can cause potential problems like obesity, depression, and reduced immune system function. According to the article of Better Health Channel (2019), It increases negative moods (anger, frustration, irritability, sadness) and decreases positive moods. Literature has extensively reported a high prevalence of poor sleep quality among medical students. However, few researchers have studied the consequences of inadequate sleep quality (Cleveland Clinic .org (2022). Supported by the OSHA (2022) Healthy Living Index Survey study, Filipinos have one of the highest rates of sleep deprivation in Asia; 46 percent of Filipinos do not get enough sleep, while 32 percent said they sleep for under six hours. Manila, Philippines: According to the 2019 Healthy Living Index Survey, Filipinos

have one of the highest rates of sleep deprivation in Asia; 46 of Filipinos do not get enough sleep, while 32 percent say they sleep for less than six hours. This mirrors a lifestyle challenge that urbanites worldwide are grappling with. In the 2019 Philips' Unfiltered Sleep: A Global Prioritization Puzzle, an international survey that looked at how people across the globe perceive, prioritize, and prepare for sleep, more than 8 in 10 adults (84 percent) say that a variety of activities take precedence over a good night's sleep.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The study's purpose was to check the information given to understand the prevalence and severity of sleep deprivation. One purpose is to assess the extent to which teachers are affected by sleep deprivation. This involves quantifying the prevalence of sleep problems among educators and gauging the severity of their sleep deficits. The study seeks to identify and analyze the underlying causes and contributing factors leading to sleep deprivation among teachers. This may include investigating workload, stressors, administrative duties, personal habits, and lifestyle choices. Another crucial purpose is to evaluate teachers' physical, mental, and emotional well-being in relation to their sleep patterns. This involves examining the health consequences, stress levels, and overall quality of life of sleep-deprived educators. The study aims to investigate how sleep deprivation affects teacher-student interactions and classroom dynamics. It seeks to understand if and how sleep-deprived teachers' irritability, patience, and effectiveness in fostering a positive learning environment are impacted. One of the central purposes is to explore how teachers' sleep deprivation may influence the personality development of their students. This involves assessing whether sleep-deprived educators are less effective in fostering qualities like empathy, emotional intelligence, and resilience in their students. In addition, the study intends to uncover the coping mechanisms teachers employ

to mitigate sleep deprivation and the types of support systems they seek or require. This information can inform the development of interventions and support programs. **Proposing Solutions and Interventions:** Based on the findings, the study aims to propose practical solutions and interventions that can help alleviate sleep deprivation among teachers. These may include recommendations for changes in school policies, workload management, and professional development programs focused on teacher well-being. A broader purpose is to underscore the societal significance of addressing sleep deprivation among educators. This involves emphasizing how the well-being of teachers is intrinsically linked to the quality of education and the holistic development of students. The study seeks to raise awareness about the issue of teacher sleep deprivation and advocate for greater recognition

of this problem within educational institutions, policy circles, and the broader community. Ultimately, the study aimed to provide valuable insights that can inform educational policies and practices to improve teacher well-being and, by extension, enhance students' educational experience and personality development. In summary, the study's purpose was to comprehensively investigate the complex relationship between teacher sleep deprivation and personality development, shedding light on the causes, consequences, and potential solutions to this critical issue in the education sector.

1.2. Research Questions—The study was to explore the unfolding story of teachers' experiences with sleep deprivation related to personality development. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are teachers' experiences towards sleep deprivation related to personality development?
- (2) How do teachers manage, and what is the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation?
- (3) 3. What educational management insights are drawn from the findings of the study?

The following terms were defined operationally to appreciate and understand this study fully.

1.3. Definition of Terms—The essential terms were described operationally: Sleep Deprivation—in this study, sleep deprivation refers to lack of sleep, which may affect the following factors, specifically personality development: Self-efficacy was the ability to produce a strongly desired or intended result. The reduced immune system refers to the functioning of the students' immune systems slowly decreasing. Frustration refers to the feeling of being upset or annoyed. The pupils' action was that they were not functioning. Behavioral skills refer to a pupil's ability to act or conduct oneself, especially towards others; they are psychologically related. Intrapersonal skills are the skills of the pupils that help them manage

emotions and cope with their problems. Interpersonal skills were the pupils' skills in terms of behaviors and tactics used to interact with others effectively. Social skills refer to the skills that students have, where any competence facilitates interaction and communication with others, where social rules and relations are created, communicated, and changed in verbal and nonverbal ways. Lastly, there were the cognitive skills, which the pupils use as the core skills of the brain to think, read, learn, remember, reason, and pay attention. Significance of the study The finding of this study was relevant to all teachers for them to be allowed to enhance themselves towards sleep deprivation related to personality development; this would also help their students to be active participants in the teaching-learning process thus, enhancing access and raising quality is another reason

to promote students' quality performance by changing the behavioral or habits in taking for granted in abstaining themselves towards sleep deprivation that may affect personality development. Through this study, we could obtain replicated data/details about sleep deprivation's impact on personality development and prove the correlation between the two variables. It was also important to inform not only the pupils' and parents' teachers but also the community about this alarming problem so that they could help implement the recommendation. Pupils: This would benefit the students as this would give them a warning about how sleep deprivation affects their excellence in school performance as long as their health. Parents: This study would also benefit the pupils' parents, as it would make them aware of the possible effect of lacking sleep on their children so that they can prevent it themselves. Teachers: This study would also benefit teachers as it would inform them about the same problems students have in connection with their performances and may be an eye-opener on how they handle them. This can also help with the teacher's health regarding not having enough sleep and management. Community: This study would also benefit the community, raising awareness of the possible negative effects of sleep deprivation and preparing them to prevent it. Readers: This study would benefit the readers as it could give them knowledge and awareness about sleep deprivation. They can apply the possible ways stated in this research to prevent sleep deprivation. Future Researchers: This study would also benefit future researchers, as it could become their reference if they choose a topic related to this study. Finally, this study's findings serve as a benchmark for future researchers, who could explore ways to integrate the important story of teachers' sleep deprivation related to pupil personality development and the development of knowledge that preserves and enhances a strong and inclusive social state.

1.4. Review of Significant Literature— Simpson and Dings (2019) reviewed studies on sleep loss and its impact on the immune system, noting behavioral and physiological changes, including fatigue and inflammation. Sleep deprivation has been linked to various health issues like depression, obesity, and cardiovascular diseases (Gimotty et al., 2020). Poor sleep quality is common among medical students and negatively affects their academic performance and cognitive functions (Maheshwari Shaukat, 2021). Adequate sleep is essential for daily refreshment, memory processing, and overall brain function (Ganpat Maheshwari, 2021).

Sleep loss impacts emotional processing from immediate responses to complex socio-emotional functioning (Ben Simon et al., 2020). It also affects self-efficacy, with gender differences indicating females are more prone to sleep disturbances and low self-efficacy (Ghose Dautovic, 2022). Research suggests that improving sleep self-efficacy could enhance sleep health (National Sleep Foundation, 2022).

Personality traits such as neuroticism are associated with poor sleep quality and increased risk of mental disorders (Clark et al., 2020; Kotov et al., 2010; Ormel et al., 2019). Most studies on sleep deprivation and personality have small sample sizes and lack comprehensive measures (Hisler et al., 2018). High neuroticism scores correlate with poor sleep hygiene and subjective sleep quality (Cheng et al., 2017; Duggan et al., 2019; Gray Watson, 2019; Williams Moroz, 2019).

Philips (2019) found that better sleep regularity correlates with higher GPA, and poor sleep can lead to decreased academic performance. Similarly, Yason et al. (2021) identified various factors affecting cognitive function and academic success, such as study habits and stress. Sleep deprivation leads to decreased motivation, empathy, and communication, contributing to academic failure (University of Santo Tomas study, 2020-2021).

Studies have highlighted the need for further research using validated measures and considering individual differences in sleep habits (Rupp et al., 2019). Sleep deprivation can also lead to increased interpersonal conflicts and poor emotional regulation (Gordon et al., ND).

Sleep is critical for physical and mental health, impacting brain function, metabolism, immune system, and cardiovascular health. Long-term sleep disruption can lead to chronic diseases like diabetes and cardiovascular issues (Medic et al., 2019). Addressing sleep disorders could enhance academic performance and overall health (Gaultney, 2016).

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored to (Dinges Kribbs, 1991). Early attempts to understand the effects of sleep deprivation focused on the “lapse hypothesis.” This theory suggested that baseline levels of functioning are identical in rested and sleep-deprived states but that sleep-deprived individuals experience transient phases of low arousal during which sleep intrusions and performance lapses occur. Although the hypothesis has some explanatory power, evidence from experiments on chronic sleep restriction (Dinges et al., 1997) suggests that it is insufficient to account for the changes in neurobehavioral functioning that occur over time (Krueger, 1993). A new theory of sleep function is presented within the context of the neuronal group selection hypothesis, which emphasizes that neuronal groups compete for neurons via use-dependent synaptic formation and atrophy. It is hypothesized that sleep serves to stabilize these competitive processes by providing a stimulation pattern that maintains a synaptic infrastructure upon which wakefulness-driven synaptic changes are superimposed. Much of the research that has examined the influence of personality on sleep deprivation has been based on (Eysenck’s 1967). Theory of personality postulates that extroverts seek stimulation while introverts are more inhib-

ited and that neurotic individuals are excitable, whereas those who are stable. Between 15 and 35 Although (Jenni et Al. 2019; Silk et Al. 2019) shows in their study the differential impact of sleep deprivation on affects across the development of adolescents age; (Ben Simoon et al., 2020) stated that sleep loss significantly impacts all levels of emotional processing, from immediate affective response to more complex socio-emotional functioning. Several scholars have pointed out the flaws in this approach; while recent research has attempted to address the problem, many of these studies have methodological flaws that limit their validity (Horne, 2019; Pilcher huffcutt 2022) and was a mounting societal problem that affects performances regardless of career, academic, and social status. To date, only a limited number of studies have examined the impact of personality on cognitive performance in sleep deprivation. (Corlozzi 2019), they claimed that Personality’s role in mediating the relationship between sleep deprivation and cognitive performance is not yet understood. Shown in Figure 1. The conceptual framework of the study. As seen in the figure, there were three interconnected variables. The unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to the personality development of pupils. Specifically, this study sought to answer teachers’ experiences of sleep deprivation related to personality development of teachers’ management and how teachers help pupils with sleep deprivation, which may generate educational management insights from the study’s findings. There was an existing concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center of the two circles determines how qualitative inquiry would connect to these studied two variables, which was influential in the unfolding story of teachers’ attitudes toward sleep deprivation related to personality development.

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study requires the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter.

2.1. Philosophical Assumption—The philosophical assumption was the theory that serves as the study’s main foundation. The collection, analysis, and interpretation of the data collected in the study were anchored in the philosophical assumptions. It would also broaden the researcher’s mind when dealing with the coming conclusions and decisions of the study. These are the typical elaborate philosophical assumptions that are used in this study. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the study is concerned with the nature of existence and structure of reality. Its philosophical consideration addresses the nature of social entities, whether they are or can be objective entities that exist independently from social actors or, instead, they were social constructions built from perceptions, actions, and interpretations of the individuals in society (Bryman, 2008). Thus, the perceptions, actions, and interpretations of the researchers, those of individuals being investigated, and those readers or audiences interpreting the study are being considered to find the existing answers to our research questions. To do so, the researcher would hold to the participants’ interpretations through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant’s answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build a construct for the

commonality and discreteness of responses. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data, the researcher must properly encode the participants’ responses from their major to the tiniest detail and must not promote personal bias in the study’s results. Epistemology. This refers to the way of understanding and explaining the researchers attain the knowledge being acquired, (Crotty, 2019). It was also ‘concerned with providing a philosophical grounding for deciding what kinds of knowledge were possible and how the researcher could ensure that the knowledge acquired were both adequate and legitimate.’ (Maynard, 2020). Hence, As a researcher, I must promote collaboration with the respondents and ensure close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that sheds light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their own interpretation in conjunction with participants’ interpretation. I upheld the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, as a researcher, I preserve the merit of

the participants' answers and carefully interpret them in light of their interpretation. Rhetoric means that I reported reality through the eyes of my research participants. This was important because it meant I was reporting objectively on what was observed and heard from the participants. The researcher in this study uses personal voice and qualitative terms such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability instead of internal and external validity and objectivity.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumption* The study utilized a qualitative research method employing a phenomenological qualitative design. According to Lester, Phenomenological research was concerned with studying experiences from the individual's perspective, "bracketing" taken-for-granted assumptions, and usual ways of perceiving. The phenomenological approach is based on a paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity. It emphasizes the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. Thus, it was decisive for understanding subjective experiences, gaining insights into participants' motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. —

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—Qualitative research was mainly associated with words, language, and experiences rather than measurements, statistics, and numerical figures. It refers to the inductive, holistic, epic, subjective, and process-oriented methods used to understand, interpret, describe, and develop a theory on a phenomenon or setting. It was a systematic, subjective approach used to describe life experiences and give them meaning (Burns Grove, 2003). The phenomenological research design was selected in this study to collect data on the live experience of the teachers' in-home visitation. The research approach would deepen understanding of the nature and the meaning of everyday experiences. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design

was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that could grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help to grasp the subject's perspective. Bryman (2008) posits that subjective and detailed personal stories could be told through interviews or face-to-face discussions, focusing on how the interviewee understands and explains different phenomena. My study aimed to draw an in-depth study of the teachers' lived experiences in conducting home visitations to students at risk of dropping. In gathering information, the researcher interviewed the participants and saturate the information through focus group discussions (FGD). Interviewing refers to structured or unstructured verbal communication between the researcher and the participants. The interview was conducted in a conducive, quiet environment, meaning it was free from disturbance, and the participants felt safe in the environment. The interview was initiated individually for about 30 to 40 minutes. In the light of the principles of decorum and standards, the researcher adheres to the following steps in the conduct of the interview and focus group discussion: make an appointment with the participants, prepare a quiet room conducive to conversation, arrange chairs to enhance a face-to-face interviewing, prepared a voice recorder, provide a jar of water. Before the interview, the researcher thanked the participants for their time and willingness to participate. The researcher reminded the participants of the agreement, explaining that the interview was unstructured and that the information the participants gave determined probing questions. The researcher must secure the permission of the participants to record the interview (Talbot, 2005).

2.4. *Research Participants*—The study's participants were the 10 public elementary school teachers purposively selected to serve as informants. The study gathered information from the elementary school teachers at New Matina Elementary Public School, Matina Dis-

trict, Division of Davao City.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—The following issues were considered in order to abide by research ethics. Before undertaking the study, the researcher sought a research clearance permit from the Division of Davao City Superintendent. Permission was also sought from the teachers' principals chosen for the study. The research must closely adhere to the participants' and informants' anonymity, confidentiality, and informed consent. Carpenter (2013) asserts that the researcher has the moral obligation to strictly consider the rights of the participants who are expected to provide knowledge. The ethical measures observed in this study include consent, confidentiality, anonymity, privacy, dissemination of results, and the right to withdraw from the study should any of the participants opt to. In such cases, the names of the participants were written in the consent, but it was not reflected in the final paper. The researcher upholds the rights of the participants and vows to establish rapport with them to ensure mutual trust and confidence.

2.6. *Role of Researcher*—This endeavor would explore the unfolding story of teachers' views on sleep deprivation related to the personality development of pupils. My role as the researcher is vital in creating credible research findings. My role is to facilitate the conduct of interviews and discussions through the research questions and probing statements. I was transcribing the data collected. I analyzed the transcription and created codes and themes from the verbal transcription. The themes were meticulously interpreted to shed light on the study's inquiry. Ethical considerations must be upheld along with the process. Further, I must strictly observe the protocol for conducting phenomenological qualitative research.

2.7. *Data Collection*—Before gathering data, I must ask for endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges to pursue the study. After the permissions

were approved by the school division Superintendent and the school principals of the target participants, the researcher talked to the participants to acquaint them with the purpose of the study. I agreed with the participants on the most convenient date and time for the interview. To start the interview, I asked the participants to read the respondents' consent forms and affix their signatures on the consent paper after they had been oriented to the study's purpose and had agreed on the terms and conditions. As a researcher, I emphasized to the respondents that they were allowed to ask questions to clarify any matter regarding the study and ask for their consent to record the course of the conversation with the assurance that everything shall be dealt with the utmost confidentiality. Through in-depth interviews, I gathered the teachers' feelings, reactions, observations, and experiences regarding their conduct toward sleep deprivation relative to the personality development of pupils. The interview included gathering information about obstacles and challenges the teachers encounter with home visitations. I likewise aimed to obtain substantial information on the impact of sleep deprivation on personality development and the interventions that help bridge the risk of health issues. In analyzing the data gathered, the participants' narratives were transcribed. According to Koontz and Weinrich (2000), the process and narratives do not need to be transcribed verbatim if the essence of the participants' communication has been captured in the transcription. The respective participants validated the individual transcriptions of the interview. To verify and revalidate the data gathered, the researcher conducted a focus group discussion to validate and triangulate the information. According to the participants' feedback, corrections may be made to ensure the meaning was conveyed in the phenomenon's fundamental structure.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—Analysis of interview transcripts begins with microanalysis; open cod-

ing based on scrutiny of data, line by line, to systematically develop concepts in terms of their themes and dimensions. Once the codes accumulated, the researcher began grouping them and categorizing them under more explanatory terms or themes (Merriam Simpson, 2000). Participants also review the findings of every interview session. According to Patton (2002), researchers can learn a great deal about the accuracy, completeness, fairness, and validity of their data analysis by having the participants described in that analysis react to what is described and concluded. Participant feedback confirms findings, confirms that each summary of the interview session is accurate, and ensures that the researcher was asking the right questions. Using the fundamental techniques of data analysis described by Dewalt and Dewalt (2002) as reading, thinking, writing, reading, rethinking, and rewriting, the researcher guarantees credible categorization, organization, and summarization of the large quantities of data obtained from this study. As the researcher developed insights into the data examined and obtained documentation to support conclusions, scholarly research was accomplished. The goal of the analysis was to develop a well-supported argument that adds to understanding a phenomenon, whether the understanding was phrased in descriptive, interpretive, or explanatory terms (Dewalt Dewalt, 2022). Preliminary analysis was carried out as the study unfolded, making the final analysis easier and less daunting. The researcher also follows recommendations to facilitate analysis described by Rossman and Rallis (2003), which included Staying connected to the general framing of the study, Asking analytic questions as you go along, and Writing all the time. Noting hunches, thoughts, and impressions, writing descriptive and analytic memos, Talking my ideas through with people. Develop a community of practice or talk with the participants; Continue to read what others have said about the topic; Use creativity; Use metaphors, creating images, drawing pictures, and drawing concept maps; Practice good management skills for data organization and accessibility; Logging daily activity, noting the date, what was done, names, times, and places; Typing field notes immediately after interviews/observations; Assigning identification codes to the data collected; Writing down attendance at events, chronologies, and descriptions; and not relying on my memory. In addition, ensuring validity and reliability was of the utmost importance to this study through careful attention to this study's conceptualization of how the data were collected, analyzed, and interpreted and how the findings are presented. Next, the researcher became familiar with the data through extensive reading of the interviews to understand the content. This involved reading through the interviews at least three times. Following Hatch's (2002) recommendations for qualitative analysis, the researcher created a sheet of notes for each participant. The summary sheets were a quick way to refer to the original data as the data analysis continued (Hatch, 2002). After the initial readings, Hatch (2002) recommends researchers read data through completely with one typology in mind. Patton (2015) defines typologies as classification systems made up of categories that divide some aspects of the world into parts. According to Hatch (2002), typologies are generated from the theory, common sense, or research objectives. For this study, the researcher used the typologies or themes from the literature review as the constructs to view the data. After reading through the data with each constructor typology in mind, the researcher coded the data into five categories from the literature by taking excerpts of text from the data and identifying it within a particular category. After everything was coded, the researcher read through the data again while writing analytic memos on her thoughts and insights and began the process of offering interpretations. During this stage, the researcher interpreted the data

to find significance and meaning in the teachers' instructional experiences by pulling salient themes, reoccurring ideas, and patterns of belief that resonated collectively throughout the interviews. The offering of interpretations began following the emergence of themes in the data. Marshall and Rossman (2006) believe this part of the data analysis brings meaning to the themes and categories and allows the researcher to develop links between the interviews. The researcher began to interpret the data to find significance and meaning in the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to the personality development of pupils. Rossman and Marshall (2006) reminded the researchers that there would always be alternate explanations existing within the data. Before moving forward, the researcher stopped and evaluated the findings for other plausible explanations. In analyzing the qualitative data, I used discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Discourse analysis focuses on the language use and patterning of the study's informants, as reflected in the detailed transcripts of recorded speech (Bueno, 2016). I transcribed and analyzed the recorded in-depth interview and focus group discussion. Part of the analysis was to determine female school leaders' challenges, coping mechanisms, and leadership behavior. It was reflected in the analytical framework in the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development was a structure as rational finding, to obtain competitive skills, personality development, and competency, carried along of pupils personality and inclination for growth development which most effective in the learning process, also the habits of pupils were affected from teachers demands, and parents supervision as what their experience to be divulged and bring new insight and hope to upcoming similar situation or case. Thematic Content Analysis was used to interpret the responses made by the key participants and determine the lessons and insights derived from the views of teach-

ers' unfolding stories about sleep deprivation and pupil personality development. Their responses were processed and conducted through analyses. Transcripts were coded in detail, with the focus shifting back and forth from the key claims of the participants to the researcher's interpretation of the meaning of the responses and subjectively interpreted. Meanwhile, the notes obtained from in-depth interviews may be transcribed immediately. The researcher may look for common themes among the responses to each question and use thematic analysis to analyze the gathered data in this phase. Their responses were processed and conducted through analysis. Transcripts were coded in detail, with the focus shifting back and forth from the key claims of the participants to the researcher's interpretation of the meaning of the responses and subjectively interpreted. Meanwhile, the notes obtained from in-depth interviews may be transcribed immediately. The researcher may be looking for common themes among the responses to each question. Environmental Triangulation. Triangulation analysis is a tool developed by Margaret Schuler to help advocates perform a strategic analysis of the issues they are working on. The tool examines three aspects: content, structure, and culture. Triangular analysis was a technique for analyzing and finding answers to a problem structured around the policy system's structure, content, and culture. It was done through transcribing, member checking, and triangulation. The entire interview transcript and add anything that might have been left out. The information may be shared with the participants in a circle to ensure we interpreted the data correctly using triangulation analysis. The researcher must possess trustworthiness and credibility to achieve a truthful and productive result in a qualitative study. With this, the researcher religiously followed the requirements (Mazuwelics, 2018).

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Qualitative research does not claim to be replica-

ble. The researcher purposefully avoids controlling the research conditions and concentrates on recording the complexity of situational contexts and interrelations as they occur naturally (Marshall Rossman, 2006). This study took many extra steps to ensure that the results from the data analysis were credible, transferable, dependable, and authentic. Credibility. Mertens (2020) defines credibility as a correspondence between how a participant perceives social constructs and how the researcher portrays the participant's viewpoints. To ensure credibility in this study, the researcher used persistent observation that allowed for long enough interviews to identify salient issues (Mertens, 2020). The researcher also monitored her developing constructions and documented any changes she experienced from the beginning of the study to the end in the analytic memos. This procedure began with the researcher's disclosure of values, beliefs, and experiences that connect her to the research topic regarding instructional practices for English learners in Elementary Mathematics. Transferability. Establishing transferability provides the degree to which the results can be generalized to other situations. The researcher kept an audit trail, which was a meticulous record of the research process so other researchers can recapture steps and the same conclusions (Mertens, 2020). Extensive and careful descriptions of the study's time, place, context, and culture were kept, developing a thick description. Not only were the data kept, but also the evidence of how the data were reduced, analyzed, and synthesized, as well as the process notes that reflect the researcher's ongoing inner thoughts, hunches, and reactions (Newton Rudestam, 2001). Conformability. "Conformability means that the data and the interpretation are not figments of the researcher's imagination" (Mertens, 2005). In this study, the data gathered would analyzed and appropriately interpreted to arrive at a convincing theme that would further discuss the importance of

the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to the personality development of pupils. To establish conformability, the researcher kept track of the qualitative data so it could be tracked to its source in the interviews. Authenticity. The researcher presents a balanced view of all perspectives, values, and beliefs to establish authenticity within the study. As a researcher, I must avoid bias in gathering the data (Newton Rudestam, 2021).

2.10. Framework for Analysis—The analytical framework for this study was flexible enough to allow the researcher to either gather all of the data and then analyze it or evaluate it while it was being collected. The data collected was then sifted, charted, and categorized in line with key topics and themes during the analysis stage. This process involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization was becoming familiar with the data through reading and re-reading interview transcripts. Familiarizing the whole interview with the audio recording and transcript and any contextual or reflective notes the researcher recorded was a vital stage in interpretation. It could also be helpful to re-listen to all or parts of the audio recording. The researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, exploring the field, or reading transcripts. The researcher would become aware of critical ideas and recurring themes throughout the procedure and would make a note of them. The researcher may be unable to review all of the material due to the enormous amount of data that might be collected in qualitative research. As a result, a portion of the data set would be utilized. Several elements of the data collection method would influence the selection. Coding was the process of summarizing and representing data to provide a systematic account of the recorded or observed phenomenon. After familiarization, the researcher carefully reads the transcript line

by line, applying a paraphrase or label that is a ‘code’ that describes what they have interpreted in the passage as necessary. Coding aimed to classify all of the data so that it could be compared systematically with other parts of the data set. Developing a thematic framework happens after coding a few transcripts. The researcher needs to compare the labels applied and select a set of codes to apply to all subsequent transcripts. Codes could be grouped into categories, which were then clearly defined. This forms a working analytical framework. Several iterations of the analytical framework were likely required before no additional codes emerged. It was always worth having another code under each category to avoid ignoring data that does not fit; the analytical framework was never ‘final’ until the last transcript had been coded. Indexing involves identifying portions or sections of data that relate to a specific theme. This procedure is conducted using all textual data collected, such as transcripts of interviews. Ritchie and Spencer (1994) suggest using a numerical system to index references and annotating them in the margin beside the text for ease. Qualitative data analysis tools were ideal for this

task. Charting involves summarizing the data by category from each transcript. Good charting requires an ability to strike a balance between reducing the data on the one hand and retaining the original meanings and ‘feel’ of the interviewees’ words on the other. The chart should include references to interesting or illustrative quotations. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, includes an analysis of the important qualities depicted in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, assisting the researcher in interpreting the data set. I must be cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis and define concepts, map the range and nature of phenomena, create typologies, find associations, provide explanations, and develop strategies (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). These concepts, technologies, and associations mirror the participant. Therefore, any strategies or recommendations the researcher offers reflect the participants’ real views, beliefs, and values. Figure 2 shows the steps in the study’s analytical framework, which involves familiarization, coding, developing a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the results of the data analysis and the discussion of the results of the study, which focused on the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development; information was gathered to examine specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: The study was to explore the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development. Before I begin my discussion, I would like to establish the symbols I used to present the quotations based on the study participants’ responses. I used codes to refer to participants of the research question in the transcriptions of the interviews. Their responses were contained and bounded around the three (3) research questions of the study. Moreover, the participants’ responses were transcribed verbatim, translated into English, encoded, and summarized in matrix form, which led to a schema. This study’s first objective is teachers’ lived experiences regarding sleep deprivation related to personality development. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, having three major themes: impact on interpersonal skills, impact on social skills, and impact on cognitive skills, that emerged after the data analysis—based on the interview data gathered from the teachers’ participants focused on the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development. The

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

transcripts of participants of the focus in depth-interview: Answer to the research question and connected to the first theme, which addresses the impact of interpersonal.

3.1. Teachers’ Lived Experiences Regarding Sleep Deprivation Related To Personality Development—

*3.1.1. Impact of Interpersonal Skills—*Research question number 1 merged with the first theme addressing the impact of interpersonal skills that were considered in the study. The lived experiences focused on the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development. The theme that was saturated during the actual discussions served as the data of participants and highlighted the addressing impact on interpersonal skills. The theme mentioned demands the learner’s needs in the learning process, supporting effective implementation focused on teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development. Participants frequently expressed concern for various responsibilities competing for the limited resources of time and energy. Therefore, based on the study’s research questions dealt

with the lived experiences focused on the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development impact on interpersonal skills. Researchers often begin with a realization of the intricate interplay between sleep quality, personality development, and interpersonal skills. Recognizing, based on the participant’s responses, that these elements are interconnected is essential for in-depth exploration. Moreover, the researcher may reflect on the high prevalence of sleep deprivation among teachers due to the profession’s demands. They would likely emphasize the need for more comprehensive studies to understand the extent of this issue and its impact on educators. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions, the lived experiences focused on the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development addressing the impact on interpersonal skills. The statement reflects their lived

experiences of focusing on the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development. Teachers led multifaceted lives, and the demands on their time and energy are significant. It was crucial to understand the various stressors and challenges they face, including irregular work hours. It might be reflected that might discover that sleep deprivation can create a vicious cycle. A lack of sleep can exacerbate stress, anxiety, or personality traits, which, in turn, can impact interpersonal relationships.

3.1.2. Aspects of Strong Social Skills—On the other hand, to mitigate the impact of sleep deprivation on my personality and interpersonal skills, I try to prioritize self-care and establish a good sleep routine. It is a work in progress, but I know the importance of being well-rested. I've learned to recognize the signs of sleep deprivation and take short breaks when I can to recharge. It's essential to communicate with colleagues and school administration when the workload becomes overwhelming. For new teachers, I would strongly advise balancing work and personal life. Don't underestimate the importance of a good night's sleep in maintaining an upbeat personality and strong interpersonal skills. New teachers should be aware of the impact of sleep on their teaching. Researchers might discover that sleep deprivation can create a vicious cycle. A lack of sleep can exacerbate stress, anxiety, or personality traits, which, in turn, can impact interpersonal relationships. Still, the study's hot problems are lived experiences focused on the unfolding story of teachers' experiences of sleep deprivation related to personality development. The theme of saturated data of participants highlighted the impact on social skills. The theme mentioned demands the learner's needs in learning, supporting effective implementation focused on teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development, addressing the impact in social skill. Understanding the coping strategies em-

ployed by teachers under sleep deprivation can provide valuable insights. This can range from self-care practices to seeking support from colleagues and friends. A key aspect is how sleep deprivation influences teaching effectiveness. A researcher might reflect on I've attended professional development sessions that addressed stress management and self-care for educators. They have been incredibly valuable in helping me maintain a positive disposition and strong social skills in the classroom. In my school, we have a supportive network of teachers who understand the challenges of sleep deprivation. We share experiences and strategies for managing it, which ultimately benefits our social skills in the classroom. As we continue to unravel this narrative, it becomes clear that investing in the health and well-being of our educators is an essential step toward nurturing the holistic development of our future generations (Hinson, 2020). Reflecting on potential preventive measures, such as educational programs on sleep hygiene and stress management for teachers, can be a part of the research journey. Researchers may need to delve into the role of school or institutional culture in contributing to or alleviating sleep-related stressors among teachers. As I analyzed the narration of participants A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6 participants based on the research questions of the study, which dealt with the lived experiences of classroom advisers, the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development Merged with the theme of aspects of strong social skills that from saturated the data of participants highlighted the addressing impact on social skills. Considering policy implications and advocating for improved working conditions, such as reasonable work hours and support for teachers' well-being, maybe a reflection point. Evidence has implicated the prefrontal cortex as a brain region that may be particularly susceptible to the effects of sleep loss. However, perplexingly, executive function tasks that putatively measure prefrontal

functioning have yielded inconsistent findings within the context of sleep deprivation (Gong et al., 2023).

3.1.3. Negative Impact in the Cognitive Skills—On the other hand, to mitigate the impact of sleep deprivation on teachers' cognitive skills, try to prioritize self-care and establish a good sleep routine. It's a work in progress, but I know the importance of being well-rested. I've learned to recognize the signs of sleep deprivation and take short breaks when I can to recharge. It was essential to communicate with colleagues and school administration when the workload became overwhelming and underestimate the importance of a good night's sleep in maintaining an upbeat personality and strong cognitive skills. Understanding the coping strategies employed by teachers under sleep deprivation can provide valuable insights. This can range from self-care practices to seeking support from colleagues and friends. Researchers could reflect on the broader policy implications of addressing sleep deprivation among teachers. They might advocate for changes in working conditions, workload management, and mental health support within the education sector. Researchers may reflect on how sleep deprivation can lead to changes in personality based on the research participants, such as increased irritability, impatience, and mood swings. They would emphasize that these changes are anecdotal and have been observed and studied in controlled settings. Here are the narrative statements of the participants. As I analyzed the narration of other participants based

on the research questions of the study dealt with the lived experiences of classroom advisers study The unfolding story of teachers' experiences with sleep deprivation related to personality development, Merged with the theme of saturated participant data, highlighted the need to address the negative impact on cognitive skills. Researchers would discuss the well-established connection between sleep and cognitive function. They might reflect on how sleep is essential for memory consolidation, problem-solving, and decision-making processes and how lack of sleep can impair these functions. Researchers could explore the implications of sleep deprivation on the teaching profession and education. They might reflect on how teachers' cognitive abilities are critical for quality education and how sleep deprivation can hinder their effectiveness. They may reflect on the importance of raising awareness about the impact of sleep deprivation on cognitive skills and personality. They might suggest that teacher professional development programs address self-care and stress management. Researchers may examine the relationship between stress, sleep deprivation, and decision-making. They might reflect on how sleep-deprived individuals tend to make more impulsive decisions and have difficulty managing stress, which can affect their personality and cognitive skills. The researcher would discuss the well-established connection between sleep and cognitive function. They might reflect on how sleep is essential for memory consolidation, problem-solving, and decision-making. Lack of sleep can impair these functions.

From the article of Cureus (Publishing et al. 2019), they proposed that sleep deprivation causes depression, agitation, apathy, and poor academic performance in students. Reduced total sleeping hours have been associated with defining academic performance. Finally, the role of emotion as a critical facet of cog-

nition has received increasing attention in recent years, and mounting evidence suggests that sleep deprivation may particularly affect cognitive systems that rely on emotional data (Physiol, 2023).Supported by the idea of Shao (2020), whereas many convergent and rule-based reasoning, decision-making, and planning tasks

Fig. 3. Thematic Framework of teacher's experience of sleep deprivation related to personality development

are relatively unaffected by sleep loss, more creative, divergent, and innovative aspects of cognition do appear to be degraded by lack of sleep. Emerging evidence suggests that some aspects of higher-level cognitive capacities remain degraded by sleep deprivation despite restoration of alertness and vigilance with stimulant countermeasures, suggesting that sleep loss may affect specific cognitive systems above and beyond the effects. Figure 3 shows the teachers' experiences with sleep deprivation related to personality development and the emergence of the standard two themes: impact on interpersonal skill, aspects of strong social skill and negative impact in cognitive skills.

3.2. *The Teacher's Coping Mechanism with The Challenges Teachers Manage And What is the Best Mechanism —*

3.2.1. *Balancing Workload*—Based on the interview data gathered from the teacher's coping mechanism with the challenges teachers manage, and what is the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation, considering the three major themes that emerged. The study's research questions dealt with the teachers' coping mechanisms with the challenges they manage and

what is the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation, considering the theme that emerged. Balancing the workload and Collaborative efforts of teachers who understand the challenges of sleep deprivation is invaluable. We share experiences and strategies for balancing workload challenges, which help maintain our effectiveness in the classroom. As I analyzed from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt with what the best mechanism is to conquer sleep deprivation, considering the research questions of the study dealt with the teacher's coping mechanism with the challenges teachers manage, and what is the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation, considering the theme that emerged: balancing workload. As a classroom adviser, by modeling an open-minded and respectful attitude, teachers' participants encourage the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation, considering the theme of balancing workload. By incorporating diverse perspectives from the narration of other participants based on the research questions of the study dealt with what the best mechanism is to conquer sleep deprivation, considering the research questions of

the study dealt with the teacher's coping mechanism with the teachers manage challenges, and what is the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation, considering the theme that emerged: balancing workload. As a classroom adviser, by modeling an open-minded and respectful attitude, teachers' participants encourage the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation, considering the themes of balancing workload and considering the theme that emerged—balancing workload. As a classroom adviser, by modeling an open-minded and respectful attitude, teachers' participants encourage the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation, considering the themes of balancing workload.

3.2.2. Teachers' Collaborative Efforts at Work—On the other hand, based on the research questions of the study dealt with the teacher's coping mechanism with the challenges teachers face and what is the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation, considering the theme that emerged with the Collaborative Efforts of Teachers who understand the challenges of sleep deprivation is invaluable. Teachers' participants share experiences and strategies for balancing workload challenges, which help maintain our effectiveness in the classroom. I analyzed the narration of other participants based on the study's research questions, which dealt with the teachers' coping mechanisms with the challenges they manage and the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation. The theme that emerged from the collaborative efforts of teachers to do their tasks at school who understand the challenges of sleep deprivation is invaluable. Teacher collaboration happens when educators create innovative lesson plans, discuss student achievement or behavior concerns,

determine student progress and challenges, and offer collegial support and encouragement in a structured environment. Teachers' participants encourage students to share their cultural backgrounds and engage in respectful conversations that explore cultural similarities and differences. By incorporating culturally diverse literature, music, and art, teachers' participants expose my students to various perspectives, fostering empathy, and promoting a sense of global citizenship. Peer support groups can significantly impact a teacher's ability to cope with challenges and maintain effectiveness in the classroom. When teachers feel heard and supported by their colleagues, it can reduce stress and foster a greater sense of resilience. Sharing experiences and strategies could lead to a collective pool of wisdom that benefits all educators involved. Considering the theme of teachers' collaborative efforts at work that emerged after data saturation. Within a supportive colleague network, constructive feedback is crucial in helping teachers improve their coping mechanisms and conquer sleep deprivation. Peers can offer suggestions and solutions based on their experiences, helping each other make positive changes in their routines and practices. Considering the theme that emerged with teachers' collaborative efforts at work who understand the challenges of sleep deprivation is invaluable. Sleep deprivation makes it difficult to process what your partner is saying in a conflict, and it can be easy to blow them off. Your brain is too tired to work through the process of conflict resolution. This can frustrate them, prolong the issue, and will frustrate them, leading to an endless cycle until you both get enough sleep (Darian, 2021).

According to the article entitled "Sleep Deprivation Impairs Your Mood and Communication Skills," sleep-deprived individuals can experience irritability, anxiety, and depression.

For example, you may avoid communicating with difficult patients or family members because you view them more negatively. You can feel confused, less vigorous, and fatigued or

Fig. 4. Teachers manage, and what is the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation

sleepy at inappropriate times. Inappropriate behavior can occur, such as giggling or laughing in serious situations. Communication skills decrease. You may fumble for the right word, say the wrong word, or misinterpret another person's words (NIOSH, 2020). Figure 5 shows the educational management insights drawn from the study and the emergence of the standard two themes: balancing workload and teachers' collaborative efforts at work.

3.3. The Educational Management Insights Drawn from The Study's Findings—The third objective of this study is educational management or insights drawn from the study's findings. The study would specifically seek to answer the question of what educational insights are drawn from the findings, which have two major themes: identifying lifestyle habits and supporting colleagues at work that emerged after the data analysis.

3.3.1. Identify Lifestyle Habits—Based on the interview data gathered from teachers' experiences regarding sleep deprivation related to personality development. The answer to research based on the study's research questions dealt with what educational management in-

sights are drawn from the study, with the theme providing additional teachers' experiences towards sleep deprivation related to personality development. From the narration of other participants, I analyzed what educational management insights were drawn from the study; they were found during the intense exchange of ideas and deepened the discussions. In instances where the first theme emerged, it identified their lifestyle habits, which means that loving what they do and actively thinking of themselves as great teachers are examples of the mindset contributing to effective teaching. Other top tips include patience, positivity, creativity, organization, compassion, humor, and respect. Most effective teachers also share a passion for life-long learning. Among other strategies, teachers can help to create a positive learning environment by establishing clear classroom rules and procedures, maintaining an environment that promotes respect, inclusivity, and diversity, and encouraging students to receive and accept constructive feedback.

3.3.2. Support Colleagues at Work—On the other hand, the narration of other participants on what educational management insights

are drawn from the study dealt with what educational management insights are drawn from the study, considering the management theme. One of the most significant aspects of supporting colleagues at work is the healing power of empathy. Teachers understanding each other's sleep deprivation challenges are more likely to offer emotional support. This empathy helps teachers manage their stress and workloads, leading to a more effective and resilient teaching force. As I analyzed the narration of other participants on what educational management insights are drawn from the study, I dealt with what educational management insights are drawn from the study, considering the theme of personality development. To conquer sleep deprivation, teachers can rely on the invaluable support of their colleagues. When sleep-deprived educators share their experiences and challenges with supportive peers, they can collaboratively develop strategies for better managing their sleep schedules. Support Colleagues at work can also alleviate the emotional toll of sleep deprivation, creating a network of understanding and empathy. Teacher collaboration allows fellow educators to meet, share insights, create cohesive plans, and work together effectively. Some of the primary purposes of collaboration are To identify educational practices that consistently help students of all abilities across classrooms and content areas. In addition, colleague support creates a sense of community and mutual understanding, allowing teachers to lean on one another for advice and emotional support. Teachers employ various coping mechanisms to manage the challenges they face. These mechanisms often include effective time management, realistic goal setting, and delegation of tasks. It is also essential for educators to prioritize self-care through regular breaks and relaxation techniques. Furthermore, an openness to change and continuous professional development are key coping strategies, allowing teachers to adapt to new teaching methods and stay current with

evolving educational practices.

3.3.3. *Teacher Personality Development—*

On the other hand, the narration of other participants on what educational management insights are drawn from the study dealt with what educational management insights are drawn from the study, considering the management theme. To help patients better monitor their condition to improve treatment outcomes, Philips also shared its cost-efficient and innovative solutions, including (DreamStation and Dreamwear. News center, 2019). , Grace (2020). Adjusting her morning and afternoon sleeping time, Grace tries to stay awake late in the evening, when the internet speed is much better, to download some of their readings and finish learning requirements. Lacking sleep duration can cause an inability to focus on work, school, and any other aspect of life, which can lead to an impending mental illness. Every individual who experiences this is advised to see a psychiatrist immediately, who can recommend what best to do. As I analyzed the narration of other participants about what educational management insights the study offers, I dealt with this question, considering the theme of teacher personality development in which personality development of teachers refers to a teacher's ability to define and make sense of their teaching practice and themselves as individuals. Personal development is a powerful tool for teachers to reach a well-defined and healthy sense of self, as they like self-concept enhancement, which can result in positive self-esteem and self-confidence. Considering the theme of personality development. Ganpat, Maheshwari and Faizan Shaukat (2021). Sleep is an essential function that allows your body and mind to recharge, leaving you refreshed and alert when you wake up. Healthy sleep also helps the body remain healthy and stave off diseases. Without enough sleep, the brain cannot function properly. This can impair your abilities to concentrate, think clearly, and process memories. Teachers employ a range of

Fig. 5. Educational management insight are drawn from the study

coping mechanisms to navigate the challenges they face, and one of the most valuable resources is the support of their colleagues. This includes sharing experiences and strategies for managing workload challenges. To achieve this personality development, teachers need to have adequate sleep to refresh the students every day and help them learn and process memory. Medical students and their facilitators should comprehend the negative effects of sleep deprivation on student academics. According to the article entitled *Impact of Poor Sleep Quality on the Academic Performance of Medical* (2020), they should take adequate measures to improve students' sleep quality. Previous research has pointed to various ways sleep impacts our social

lives. A 2019 study found that people experience more interpersonal conflict the day after a poor night's sleep. Another found that participants showed lower empathetic accuracy and were worse at conflict resolution in a lab-based task after sleeping poorly. People who have slept poorly are less accurate at identifying the emotions on strangers' faces and are more likely to stereotype strangers, including rating White-sounding names as more qualified than Black-sounding ones during a hypothetical hiring exercise. Figure 5 shows the educational management insights drawn from the study and the emergence of the standard three themes: identify lifestyle habits, support colleagues at work, and teacher personality development.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on its findings. Future directions in the field of culturally responsive teachers through the lens of classroom advisers are also discussed here. In addition it, the participants of the study are the 10 public elementary school teachers who will be purposively selected to serve as informants. The study was gathering information from the elementary school teachers at New Matina Elementary Public School, Matina District, Division of Davao City. To be considered as participants. The study was to explore the unfolding story of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: What are the experiences of teachers towards sleep deprivation related to personality development? How do teachers manage sleep deprivation related to personality development? What educational

management insights are drawn from the study findings? These results may provide foundational information to guide the district in addressing the local issue. Identify lifestyle habits, personality development, and management.

4.1. Findings—The findings revealed that this study’s first objective is teachers’ lived experiences regarding sleep deprivation related to personality development. The study would specifically seek to answer the following queries, which have three major themes: impact on interpersonal skills, aspects of socially solid skills, and last negative impact on cognitive skills. The second objective of this study was to determine the teachers’ coping mechanisms with the challenges they manage and the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation, considering the two major themes of balancing workload and teachers’ collaborative efforts at work. The third objective of this study was educational management or insights are drawn from the findings of the study. The study would specifically seek to answer the queries of what educational insights are drawn from the findings of the study, which have three major themes: Identify lifestyle habits, Support Colleagues at work, and Teacher Personality Development. Understanding the link between sleep deprivation and personality development underscores the need for a holistic approach to education. It emphasizes that student well-being is not limited to academic success but includes their overall physical and emotional health. The research could highlight the need for teachers to be more aware of and sensitive to their students’ sleep patterns and habits. Understanding the extent of sleep deprivation and its effects on personality development is the first step toward addressing the issue effectively. It underscores the importance of creating a classroom environment that prioritizes students’ well-being, including their sleep needs. Teachers can play a crucial role in fostering a supportive atmosphere where students feel comfortable discussing their sleep-related concerns. Identifying signs of

sleep deprivation and its potential impact on personality development can lead to early intervention. Teachers can collaborate with parents and school counselors to address these concerns promptly. The research can inform educational policies at the school or district level. It may encourage schools to consider factors like start times and scheduling to ensure students have the opportunity for adequate sleep. Teachers may benefit from professional development and training on recognizing and addressing sleep-related issues. This can empower them with the knowledge and skills to support students in improving their sleep habits. The findings can encourage open communication between teachers and parents regarding students’ sleep needs. Teachers can collaborate with parents to ensure students have a conducive sleep environment at home.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The teachers’ lived experiences regarding sleep deprivation related to personality development have three major themes: impact on interpersonal skills, aspects of socially solid skills, and negative impact on cognitive skills. While the teachers’ coping mechanisms with the challenges they manage and the best mechanism to conquer sleep deprivation consider the two major themes of balancing workload and teachers’ collaborative efforts at work. Educational management or insights are drawn from the study’s findings, which have three major themes: Identify lifestyle habits, Support Colleagues at work, and Teacher Personality Development. Understanding the link between sleep deprivation and personality development underscores the need for a holistic approach to education.

4.3. Future Directions—The study results have implications for teachers, students, parents,

and educational institutions. It emphasizes the need for a comprehensive approach to education that considers the well-being of students, including their sleep needs and potential impact on personality development. A solid basis for the Department of Education looking ahead, there were several future directions and considerations for responsive teachers as they continue to evolve their practice and navigate the complexities of education. The research could guide the development of evidence-based interventions or programs to improve students' sleep quality. These interventions could be tailored to address personality development concerns. Teachers can become advocates for promoting healthy sleep habits among students. This may involve incorporating lessons or discussions on the importance of sleep in their curriculum. The findings can encourage open communication between teachers and parents regarding students' sleep needs. Teachers can collaborate with parents to ensure students have a conducive sleep environment at home. Teachers may consider the result to help them in addressing the stress in handling their students. The finding of this study was relevant to all teachers for them to be allowed to enhance themselves towards sleep deprivation related to personality development; this would also help their students to be active participants in the teaching-learning process thus, enhancing access and raising quality is another reason to promote students' qual-

ity performance by changing the behavioral or habits in taking for granted in abstaining themselves towards sleep deprivation that may affect personality development. Through this study, we could obtain replicated data/details about sleep deprivation's impact on personality development and prove the correlation between the two variables. It was also essential to inform not only the pupils' and parents' teachers but also the community about this alarming problem so that they could help implement the recommendation. This could also help with the teacher's health regarding not having enough sleep and management. Community: This study would also benefit the community, raising awareness of the possible negative effects of sleep deprivation and preparing them to prevent it. This study would benefit the readers as it could give them knowledge and awareness about sleep deprivation. They could apply the possible ways stated in this research to prevent sleep deprivation. Future Researchers: This study would also benefit future researchers, as it could become their reference if they choose a topic related to this study. Finally, this study's findings serve as a benchmark for future researchers, who could explore ways to integrate the important story of teachers' sleep deprivation related to pupil personality development and the development of knowledge that preserves and enhances a strong and inclusive social state.

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